

THE ROLE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FIGHTER SPEECH

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Abstract.

This article discusses the pedagogical and educational benefit of teaching younger kids phraseological units, teaching techniques, and the significance of phraseological units in the development of students' speech.

Fundamental words and phrases: syntactic units, characteristics of the similarities and mutual differences of content-stable compound words, methods of grouping classes for working on proverbs.

The education system is being revised even before elementary school, in compliance with the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Language,"

"On Education," and the "National Personnel Training Program." The fundamental purpose of teaching the topic of the local language in primary school is to allow pupils to express themselves freely and effectively in writing and vocally, to consciously learn the norms of the Uzbek language, and to gain theoretical knowledge. Its goal is to build a person who understands how to use the language appropriately and has a developed speech culture.

That is all. Simultaneously, in updating educational content, the principle "the student is an active participant in the learning process" has changed, necessitating a non-traditional organization of the educational process using modern pedagogical technologies., enhance students' free creativity and independent study. First and foremost, the development of speech happens in response to these needs. The major ways of improving kids' speech are lexical units - words and phraseological units (phrases), figurative expressions. The fundamental job of elementary school instructors is to improve the speech of younger pupils, which is mostly accomplished via the teaching of the subjects "Mother tongue" and "Reading." The function and significance of lexical and phraseological work in the system of developing pupils' speech is recognized. The components of students' speech competency are produced on the basis of lexical and phraseological works based on the needs of general secondary education (particularly elementary education) of the DTS and the curriculum. That is, while evaluating the texts in the "Native Language" and "Reading" textbooks for grades 1-4, the following lexical and phraseological work should

be performed: 1. The mutual distinction of lexical and phraseological components. 2. Practice your vocabulary. 3. A lexico-analytical examination. When identifying lexico-semantic units, the emphasis is on teaching phraseological units (PU). In texts delivered in the original language and in primary school reading textbooks, phraseologisms are actively utilized alongside lexical units, and a specific study of these units adds to the development of students' speech, eloquence, and aesthetic thinking. cultivation. Important features of FB training include: - pupils becoming acquainted with the characteristics of FB; - learning to differentiate FB from other lexical units; - learning to separate FB from syntactic units (sentences);

- On the basis of Facebook, students' speeches evolve. While there is no distinct hour (lesson) on the subject of phraseological units, which have been extensively utilized in our language for millennia as metaphorical representations of thinking, the capacity to acquire and employ phraseological units effectively in speech is taught in lessons. Working on a sentence, working on a text, parsing texts, creating speech, and learning coherent speech may all be developed during the school year. In reality, the capacity to employ FB in speech is critical in the development of students' creative thinking and speech, as well as in consolidating their knowledge on the subject and molding the ability to apply them effectively and responsibly. To be used in native language and reading instruction. At the same time, the teacher must first understand and assimilate the specific lexico-semantic, methodological features of the FB, active and inactive types based on their use, similarities and differences of lexical and syntactic units, and be able to use new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods. The teaching of phraseological units is done in phases. At the first level, first notions about the specific aspects of FB, particularly their lexico-semantic meanings, are created. This is accomplished mostly via actual work and, to a lesser extent, by theoretical issues. In the first level, researchers investigate how FB vary from lexical units such as words, compound words, and stable compound words such as proverbs, aphorisms, and figurative expressions. prof. According to A. A. Yuldoshev's perspective, it is best to understand the similarities and differences of lexical and phraseological units via an exercise system. A. A. Yuldoshev, Ph.D. "The phrases treated as phraseological units are similar to lexical units, particularly compound words with certain properties." He contends that the distinction between phraseological units and compound words is semantic-functional, rather than structural, and hence methodologically clear" [4, 214]. The lexical meaning of a

compound word is communicated directly, rather than via an image, in the FB, however, the meaning is represented through a metaphor, and the nominative - proper (atash) is based on meanings. In reality, although the right (proper) meaning is the leading one in words (compound words), the figurative-nominative meaning is the main one in FS, where the figurative meaning is a universal characteristic. Younger pupils should be taught the distinctions between these units based on their age and grade level. Simultaneously, the ability to differentiate each unit - a word, a compound word, a proverb, an aphorism based on its unique characteristics - is developed. Hence, FB may be characterized as "lexical units" of phrases, "complex words in the form of a phrase similar to a sentence," and "in general, one can learn to discern between stable compounds (proverbs, proverbs, and aphorisms) with the proper value via methodical exercises." The talent of differentiating FBs from syntactic units - phrases, sentences, distinguishing FBs employed in texts, their location of use and functions in speech, particularly in linked speech, is created at the final stage; it is meaningless if it is only partly taught theoretically. According to Yuldoshev, phraseological compounds are structurally similar to syntactic units only in origin. prof. S. N. Muratov separates FB from free phrases based on the following characteristics: 1) semantic consistency; 2) imagery; and 3) portability [6,130]. One of the most important aspects of speech development in elementary school is vocabulary practice. At the same time, stable compounds employed in texts of grades 1-4 of the local language and reading textbooks are used to motivate pupils in connection with reading, recounting a work of art, researching the topic, preparing for presentation and essay. Working on vocabulary, using dictionaries to work on the meaning of words and FB unfamiliar to students, conducting lessons on studying the meaning of phraseological combinations, and using various types of vocabulary exercises, you can determine the level of students' ability to distinguish between FB (phrase) and phrase. The development of younger schoolchildren's speech through lexico-linguistic analysis is dependent on three main factors: first, paying attention to the selection of words and FB from the text, as well as the correct and expressive speech of children, i.e., the conditions of speech; second, how children's speech experience is organized; and third, the teacher's ability to rely on elements of lexicology and phraseology, as well as the theory of language. As a result, while teaching FB to younger schoolchildren, it is recommended that FB be used in pupils' speech to develop the abilities of appropriately reading their meanings. Learn to use particular examples to illustrate the difference

between FB and words, compound words, and phrases; this will be a solution to the issue of boosting the beauty and efficacy of students' speaking.

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